

EFFECTS OF MOISTURE CONTENT ON THE THERMAL EXPANSION STRAIN OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A systematic experimental work is conducted to investigate the effects of moisture contents on the thermal expansion strain of carbon/epoxy composites. The moisture content of the composite is determined by immersing the specimen into the water until a stable moisture content is reached. The moisture content of the experimental data agrees well with the moisture diffusion law. The longitudinal and transverse thermal expansion strains of the wet composites with various laminations are measured using the strain gage method. The thermal expansion strain is dependent on the fiber orientations and fiber contents in longitudinal and transverse directions.

INTRODUCTION

Owing to their favorable performance characteristics, fiber reinforced composite materials have been gaining wide use in commercial, military and space applications. In order to utilize their full advantage, the effects of environmental conditions on the mechanical behavior of the composite materials must be known during their entire service life. Information on the response of composite materials subject to environmental conditions should be useful in the design of composite elements and structures.

Concerning the moisture absorption of composite materials, Shen and Springer [1] proposed the one dimensional moisture diffusion law. The moisture diffusion law has been modified by several investigators to study the moisture contents of composite materials under different environmental conditions [2-4]. The influence of moisture content on the degradation of composite materials has been found important in recent years. Shen and Springer [5,6] investigated the effects of moisture and temperature on the tensile strength and elastic moduli of composite materials. The effects of moisture on the mechanical properties of high-performance structural composites were investigated by Browning and Hartness [7]. They observed that moisture has significant reduction to the flexural strength of a unidirectional composite. Schanz and Kress [8] found that the environmental conditions induced hygroscopic stresses have some effects on the edge delamination of composite materials, and hence reduce the strength of the structural member. Bouadi and Sun [9] developed a three dimensional finite element program to predict the stress field of laminated composite under the hygrothermal change and the stress distribution may cause the failure of the laminate.

In the thermal expansion behavior of composite materials, Tompkins *et. al.* [10] applied the laser-interferometric dilatometer to measure the thermal expansion strain of continuous fiber reinforced unidirectional composites. Bowles and Tompkins [11] employed several analytical models to predict the longitudinal and transverse coefficients of thermal expansion of unidirectional composites. The predicted results were compared with each other and with experimental results. A sensitivity analysis was also conducted by them to determine the relative influence of constituent properties on the coefficients of thermal expansion. Gdoutos *et. al.* [12] employed experimental method and analytical model to study the thermal expansion behavior of a silicon carbide/aluminum composite. Millen and De Witt [13] have used strain gages and thermocouples to measure the coefficients of thermal expansion of composites. A very detailed description about the measuring technique was presented.

In the present study, A systematic experimental work is conducted to investigate the effects of moisture content on the thermal expansion strain and the coefficients of thermal expansion of carbon/epoxy laminates. The moisture content of the composite specimens is determined by immersing the specimens into the natural water of constant temperature until a stable moisture content is reached. The effects of laminate thickness and ply orientation on the moisture absorption capacity are also investigated. The longitudinal and transverse thermal expansion strains of the dry and wet composite specimens with various laminations and thickness are measured by using the strain gage method. The effects of moisture content on the thermal expansion strains are investigated. The thermal expansion strain is dependent on the fiber directions and fiber contents in longitudinal and transverse directions. The effects of temperature on the thermal expansion strains are also conducted.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials used for thermal expansion test are made from carbon/epoxy prepreg tapes with carbon fibers supplied by the Asahikasei Carbon Fiber Co. 300 mm by 300 mm square unidirectional and symmetric cross-ply laminated plates are fabricated by a hand lay up and vacuum bag process in the laboratory. After cure, each laminate is cut into specimens with dimensions of 120 mm by 75 mm by using a water cooled diamond saw. The dimensions of the specimens used here to measure the thermal expansion strains can ensure that the specimens are large enough to locate the strain gages to avoid edge effects and discontinuities [13]. The rectangular shape ensures positive coordinate control. The fiber orientation and thickness of the test specimens are listed in Table 1. After cutting, the specimens are numbered, weighed, and measured. Then they are stored in room temperature desiccator.

For the moisture absorption of carbon/epoxy laminated plates, the specimens are immersed in natural water in tank. The temperature of the water is kept in $17.5 \pm 1^{\circ}C$. The measurements are conducted for 100 days with the specimens being weighed about every 4 days. The moisture content is measured in percent. The moisture contents are plotted as a function of square root of time (\sqrt{t}). The relation between the moisture content and square root of time is linear in a short period of time of immersion. The moisture content will reach to stable around after 80 days of immersion.

In general, the thermal expansion strain measurements are usually required in both the $x(0^{\circ})$ and $y(90^{\circ})$ directions. The repeatability of stacked bi-axial gages is not as good as individual gages. Each grid of unstacked bi-axial gages has different gage factor, transverse sensitivity, and apparent strain characteristic, the chances for mistakes are increasing during test [13]. Therefore,

in the present study, individual gages will be used to measure the thermal expansion strain. Since the coefficient of thermal expansion in $x(0^\circ)$ and $y(90^\circ)$ directions of a unidirectional composite are different and the STC (self-temperature-compensation) number of the strain gage will affect the apparent strain curves referenced to titanium silicate. 00 STC strain gage will be used in the $x(0^\circ)$ direction measurement and 13 STC strain gage will be used in the $y(90^\circ)$ direction measurement for the present study. From above-mentioned facts, two Micromerement WK-00-500 BH-350 strain gages will be bonded on the center of each specimen, one to each face, by using M bond-600 to measure the longitudinal thermal expansion strain and WK-13-500 BH-350 strain gages will be bonded on the specimen in the same way to measure the transverse thermal expansion strain. Since moisture will affect the measurement of thermal expansion strain, the mounted strain gage will be coated with 3140 RTV coating to protect the strain gage.

Thermal expansion tests are conducted in the cold heat climate test chamber. The composite specimen and the referenced titanium silicate are connected to SB-10 switch and balance unit and to P-3800 strain indicator. The procedure in the thermal expansion measurements is to heat the specimens in steps, allowing thermal equilibrium to occur at each intervening temperature. The thermal cycle for the present measurements is cooled the specimen from room temperature ($20^\circ C$) to $-30^\circ C$, and then heated to $100^\circ C$ with heating rate $1.1^\circ C/min$. In each $10^\circ C$ temperature change, the chamber temperature is holding for 1 hour, and the output of the strain indicator and temperature is recorded. After test, the strain gage data is corrected and plots the results with the specimen temperature.

Table 1. Lamination and thickness of the test specimens

Designation	Lamination	Thickness (mm)
U1	$[0]_5$	0.80 ± 0.05
L1	$[0/90/0/90/0]$	0.75 ± 0.05
U2	$[0]_{10}$	1.45 ± 0.05
L2	$[0_2/90_2/0_2/90_2/0_2]$	1.35 ± 0.05
L3	$[0_5/90_5/0_5]$	2.25 ± 0.05
L4	$[0/90/0 \dots 0/90/0]$	2.20 ± 0.05

MOISTURE CONTENT OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

The moisture contents of unidirectional and cross-ply laminates as a function of square root of time are presented in this section. Fig. 1 shows the moisture contents of unidirectional laminates, U1 and U2, as a function of square root of time. Due to the fact that thicker laminate has more epoxy material, the moisture absorption capacity is higher in thick laminate. Fig. 2 shows the effect of ply orientation on the moisture content of composite. Unidirectional laminate is exhibiting more moisture content than the cross-ply laminate for the same period of immersion time. The moisture absorption in the specimens is dependent on the direction of fibers, and the epoxy material typically has higher moisture absorption capacity than the fiber. From above results, it is also noticed that the moisture content is proportional to the square root of time in a short period after the specimen being immersed into the water. It is agreed to the description of moisture diffusion law [5].

THERMAL EXPANSION OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

After the test specimen has been immersed into the water for 100 days, the specimen is conducting a thermal expansion experiment in the cold heat climate test chamber to investigate the effects of moisture content on the thermal expansion strain of carbon/epoxy composite. Fig. 3 contains the variation of longitudinal thermal expansion strain with the temperature of the wet unidirectional composite. The longitudinal thermal expansion strain of dry composite is also included for comparison. The transverse thermal expansion strain of same composite is shown in Fig. 4. From the test data, it is found that average longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion of dry composite is $0.4 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the average transverse coefficient of thermal expansion is $30.2 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion of wet composite is $-0.46 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the transverse coefficient of thermal expansion is $28.4 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The moisture will reduce the average transverse coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite. It is also noticed that the moisture content has little effect on the longitudinal thermal expansion strain of a unidirectional composite at room temperature.

Figs. 5 and 6 are the longitudinal and transverse thermal expansion strain of dry unidirectional, U2, and cross-ply, L2, laminates. Due to the fact that cross-ply laminate contains 60 % matrix and 40 % fibers in the transverse direction of the laminate and the coefficient of thermal expansion of epoxy material is higher than fiber, the transverse thermal expansion strain of cross-ply laminate is lower than that of unidirectional laminate. The thermal expansion strain of wet unidirectional and cross-ply laminates are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. It is observed that the transverse thermal expansion strain of carbon/epoxy composite has been reduced when the composite has absorbed some moisture. It is also found that the moisture content will have more effect on the mechanical properties of unidirectional laminate than on the cross-ply laminate.

The longitudinal and transverse thermal expansion strain of cross-ply laminates, L3 and L4, are shown in Figs. 9 and 10. The thermal expansion strain is affected significantly by the fraction of fibers in each direction. Since L3 has less fibers in the transverse direction than L4, so that L3 has higher transverse thermal expansion strain. The thermal expansion strains are also affected by the temperature of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

A systematic experimental work is conducted to investigate the effects of moisture content on the thermal expansion strain and the coefficient of thermal expansion of carbon/epoxy composites. The moisture content of the composite is determined by immersing the specimen into the water for 100 days until a stable moisture content is reached. Due to the fact that epoxy material has higher absorption capacity, the moisture content in the unidirectional laminate is higher than in the cross-ply laminate for the same period of immersion time. The moisture content in the composite is proportional to the square root of time. It agrees well with the moisture diffusion law.

The thermal expansion experiment is conducted in a cold heat climate test chamber by using the strain gage method. It is found that the moisture content has effect on the thermal expansion strain and the coefficient of thermal expansion of a composite. The coefficient of thermal expansion of a wet composite is lower than that of a dry composite. The thermal expansion strain is dependent on the fiber orientations and fiber contents in the longitudinal and transverse directions. For the same thickness unidirectional and cross-ply laminates, the transverse thermal expansion strain of a unidirectional laminate is higher than that of a cross-ply laminate. In a unidirectional laminate, the moisture content has little effect on the longitudinal thermal expansion strain. The thermal expansion strains are also affected by the temperature of the composite.

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Figure 1. Moisture contents versus time of unidirectional laminates.

Figure 2. Moisture contents versus time of unidirectional and cross-ply laminates.

Figure 3. Longitudinal thermal expansion strain of dry and wet unidirectional laminates.

Figure 4. Transverse thermal expansion strain of dry and wet unidirectional laminates.

Figure 5. Longitudinal thermal expansion strain of dry unidirectional (U2) and cross-ply (L2) laminates.

Figure 6. Transverse thermal expansion strain of dry unidirectional (U2) and cross-ply (L2) laminates.

Figure 7. Longitudinal thermal expansion strain of wet unidirectional (U2) and cross-ply (L2) laminates.

Figure 8. Transverse thermal expansion strain of wet unidirectional (U2) and cross-ply (L2) laminates.

Figure 9. Longitudinal thermal expansion strain of wet cross-ply (L3 and L4) laminates.

Figure 10. Transverse thermal expansion strain of wet cross-ply (L3 and L4) laminates.